

Co-designing the Policy Cloud for intelligent policies in the agrifood industry

Sentiment Analysis for the Aragon Wine Industry

The workshop for the Policy Cloud “Intelligent policies for the development of agrifood industry” (Aragon) was held on 28th November 2021 in Zaragoza. During the event, scenario B (Opinions on social media) was evaluated by a group of policy makers, data analysts and domain experts. This scenario has already been implemented in other use cases.

20 Participants 12 Male & 8 Female

Role 5 Policy Makers, 3 Data Analysts, 10 Domain Experts, 2 Other.

Requirements

What are the most common problems policy makers face in their daily operation?

Lack of data, coexistence among data.

Data are very distributed, and it is difficult to find correlations.

Difficult to access data.

What is the information that lack policy makers in handling evidence-based policies?

Data is not always available in a standardised format.

Centralization and communication.

What is your opinion about creating an online platform to support policy makers?

It improves the way to access information and share it.

It makes it easier to work with data.

Policy Cloud Platform evaluation

How successful is the Policy Cloud platform in performing the intended tasks?

12 Moderately satisfied

7 Slightly satisfied

1 Very satisfied

0 Not at all satisfied

Policy Evaluation

How easy is it to create a Policy Model using the Policy Cloud platform?

How easy is it to assess the KPIs using the Policy Cloud platform?

Scenario Evaluation

This system's capabilities meet my requirements.

Overall, the system is useful for daily operations.

What would you do to improve the tool?

Improving interaction: Allow policy makers choose their graphs.

More explanation about what is shown on screen

People need to study the tool, work with it, and study all the scenarios in order to have an opinion.

End-users want to have the ability to interact with a live demo in order to be in a position to provide a more extensive opinion about it.

Improving interaction with the graphical tool in order to build KPIs and study results

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